

(*Poecilia reticulata*) hosts can drive differences in the aggregation of *Gyrodactylus* spp. parasites among their hosts.

For the Limpet-barnacle part of the analysis, we are using the unpublished data set limpetbarnacle.csv. This file contains the following variables:

Site: A factor that identifies the site where the community was collected.

QUADRAT: A factor that identifies the quadrat site location of each community of limpets and barnacles. It has a level per community.

H: The total number of limpet hosts in each community

P: The total number of barnacle symbionts in each community

MeanP: The mean abundance of barnacles living on the limpets for each community.

varP: The variance in abundance of barnacles living on the limpets for each population.

MeanW: The mean width measurement for the limpets in each community. Measured in (*millimeters*)

VarW: The variance in width measurement for the limpets in each community. Measured in (*millimeters*²)

MeanL: The mean length measurement for the limpets in each community. Measured in (*millimeters*)

VarL: The variance in length measurement for the limpets in each community. Measured in (*millimeters*²)

fs var log med: The log median variance predicted by the feasible set for each limpet-barnacle community.

For the guppy-Gyrodactlid portion of the manuscript we are using the guppygyro.csv dataset. This data is a combination of population level data from Stephenson, J. F., Oosterhout, C. van, Mohammed, R. S. & Cable, J. Parasites of Trinidadian guppies: evidence for sex- and age-specific trait-mediated indirect effects of predators. *Ecology* 96, 489–498 (2015) and an additional, unpublished data set which contains the following variables:

Site: A factor that identifies the drainage, river, course, site, and year the population data was taken. It has a level per population.

drainage: The drainage where the population was collected from. Six levels

river: The river where the population was collected from. 13 levels.

year: The year the population was collected in. 5 levels.

season: The season the population was collected. 2 levels.

Course: The watercourse the population was collected in. 2 levels. Upper indicates low predation populations while lower indicates high predation populations in line with previous publications from the Trinidadian guppy system

H: The total number of hosts in the population

P: The total number of parasites in the population

MeanP: The mean number of parasites infecting hosts in the population

VarP: The mean number of parasites infecting hosts in the population

MeanLen: The mean length of all individuals in the population (*millimeters*)

VarLen: The variance in length of the population (*millimeters*²)

MeanW: The mean weight of all individuals in the population (*grams*)

VarW: The variance in weight of the population (*grams*²)

fs var log med: The log median variance predicted by the feasible set.

sex: The sex of individuals in the population. Populations were separated into males and females to conduct each analysis and calculate body condition. This allowed us to better understand aggregation differences between sexes. 2 levels.

jonvar: The variation in condition of individuals in the population

ResBC: The body condition given the residual mass index.

jonres: The residual of a regression between the body condition given by index from Johnson et al. 2011 and the mean length of the population. We did this to control for any body condition bias we may see between populations just due to size differences.

diffvar: The difference in variances between the observed and expected distribution (the feasible set) of parasites in the population. Positive values indicates the population has a higher variance (More aggregation) than expected by the feasible set, negative values means the feasible set predicted more variance than is present in the observed data

logMean: The log10 mean of parasites in the population.
jonresRS: The scaled jonres variable from above.
MeanLenRS: The scaled mean length variable from above.
ExpPrev: The expected prevalence of the population given by the feasible set
ObsPrev: The observed prevalence of the population
MaxF: The expected number of parasites on the individual with the highest parasite burden in the population given by the feasible set
MaxE: The observed number of parasites on the individual with the highest parasite burden in the population

We additionally have a separate CSV file named “guppysexescorr.csv.” This dataset is just a subset of the larger guppy dataset to test for correlations between the aggregation of parasites between males and female guppies from the same site.

1.1 Load necessary packages and data

```
# Clear the working environment
rm(list = ls())

# Load in the necessary packages
library(plyr)
library(secr)
library(lmtest)
library(ggplot2)
library(DHARMa)
library(tidyverse)
library(car)
library(glmmTMB)
library(lme4)
require(visreg)
require(arm)
library(readr)
library(performance)
source("http://highstat.com/Books/BGS/GAMM/RCodeP2/HighstatLibV6.R")
library(viridis)
library(RColorBrewer)
require(simr)
library(r2glmm)
library(gridExtra)
library(lmerTest)

# dataframe containing all the data for the Guppy-gyrodactylus
# portion of the manuscript
FS_trin <- read.csv("guppygyro.csv")
# dataframe containing all the data for the Limpet-Barnacle portion
# of the analysis
Limp <- read.csv("limpetbarnacle.csv")
Limp$fs_var_log_med <- as.numeric(Limp$fs_var_log_med)
Limp <- subset(Limp, fs_var_log_med > -Inf)
Limp <- subset(Limp, H > 4 & P > 5)
summary(Limp)
```

```

##      Site                QUADRAT                H                P
## Length:303          Length:303          Min.   : 5.00          Min.   : 6.00
## Class :character    Class :character    1st Qu.: 12.50         1st Qu.: 27.00
## Mode  :character    Mode  :character    Median : 19.00         Median : 52.00
##                                     Mean  : 20.68          Mean  : 82.33
##                                     3rd Qu.: 26.00         3rd Qu.:100.50
##                                     Max.  :115.00          Max.  :802.00
##      MeanP                varP                MeanW                VarW
## Min.   : 0.07826          Min.   : 0.0728          Min.   : 7.00          Min.   : 3.839
## 1st Qu.: 1.55084          1st Qu.: 5.6315          1st Qu.:12.64          1st Qu.: 26.424
## Median : 3.00000          Median : 20.8738          Median :15.79          Median : 55.622
## Mean   : 4.69978          Mean   : 62.4280          Mean   :16.10          Mean   : 72.932
## 3rd Qu.: 5.81136          3rd Qu.: 60.4044          3rd Qu.:19.13          3rd Qu.: 96.947
## Max.   :34.00000          Max.   :1308.9706          Max.   :27.80          Max.   :333.331
##      MeanL                VarL                fs_var_log_med          MeanCA
## Min.   : 7.929           Min.   : 1.50           Min.   : -0.6904          Min.   : 166.5
## 1st Qu.:14.571           1st Qu.: 24.64          1st Qu.: 0.8042          1st Qu.: 448.7
## Median :18.227           Median : 43.43          Median : 1.2167          Median : 622.3
## Mean   :18.958           Mean   : 51.31          Mean   : 1.2211          Mean   : 687.2
## 3rd Qu.:23.000           3rd Qu.: 68.89          3rd Qu.: 1.6913          3rd Qu.: 909.6
## Max.   :34.750           Max.   :195.66          Max.   : 2.9900          Max.   :1546.8
##      VarCA
## Min.   : 3443
## 1st Qu.: 40360
## Median : 89549
## Mean   :127965
## 3rd Qu.:176029
## Max.   :768821

```

```
FeasCorr <- read.csv("guppysexescorr.csv")
```

1.1.1 Setting variables as factors and calculating important metrics

```

# Setting factors as factors setting each factor as a sum contrast to
# make interpretation easier.
FS_trin$Site <- stats::C(base::factor(FS_trin$Site), sum)
FS_trin$Course <- stats::C(base::factor(FS_trin$Course), sum)
FS_trin$sex <- stats::C(base::factor(FS_trin$sex), sum)

# Calculating the difference in the Observed prevalence in each each
# population with that predicted by the feasible set
FS_trin$DiffPrev <- FS_trin$ObsPrev - FS_trin$ExpPrev

# Calculating the ratio of max parasite burden between the feasible
# set and the observed data
FS_trin$DiffPRatio <- FS_trin$MaxE/FS_trin$MaxF
# Calculating the difference in variance between the observed
# distributions and that of the feasible set for the Limpets
Limp$diffvar <- log10(Limp$varP) - Limp$fs_var_log_med
# Categorical factor for plotting
Limp$L <- "Limpets"

```

```

# Creating the Variance in length regression by sex and extracting
# the residuals
FS_trin$VarLenR <- residuals(lm(VarLen ~ sex, FS_trin))

# Scaling and Centering
FS_trin$jonvarRS <- as.numeric(scale(FS_trin$jonvar))
FS_trin$logMeanRS <- as.numeric(scale(FS_trin$logMean))
FS_trin$MeanLenRS <- as.numeric(scale(FS_trin$MeanLen))
FS_trin$VarLenRS <- as.numeric(scale(FS_trin$VarLenR))
FS_trin$jonresRS <- as.numeric(scale(FS_trin$jonres))
Limp$MeanLRS <- as.numeric(scale(Limp$MeanL))
Limp$VarLRS <- as.numeric(scale(Limp$VarL))
Limp$MeanWRS <- as.numeric(scale(Limp$MeanW))
Limp$VarWRS <- as.numeric(scale(Limp$VarW))
# importing Gotanda et al. and Martin and Johnsen data for comparison
tpl_data_MJ_males <- read_csv("~/Desktop/Projects/DataforGuppy-GyroAgg/Data/tpl_data_MJ_males.csv")
tpl_data_Go_males <- read_csv("~/Desktop/Projects/DataforGuppy-GyroAgg/Data/tpl_data_Go_males.csv")
tpl_data_Go_females <- read_csv("~/Desktop/Projects/DataforGuppy-GyroAgg/Data/tpl_data_Go_females.csv")

# Calculating the difference in variance for each of the new datasets
tpl_data_Go_females$Sex <- "F"
tpl_data_Go_females$logVar <- log10(tpl_data_Go_females$VarP)
tpl_data_Go_males$logVar <- log10(tpl_data_Go_males$VarP)
tpl_data_Go_females$diffvar <- (tpl_data_Go_females$logVar - tpl_data_Go_females$fs_var_log_med)
tpl_data_Go_males$diffvar <- (tpl_data_Go_males$logVar - tpl_data_Go_males$fs_var_log_med)
tpl_data_MJ_males$logVar <- log10(tpl_data_MJ_males$VarP)
tpl_data_MJ_males$diffvar <- (tpl_data_MJ_males$logVar - tpl_data_MJ_males$fs_var_log_med)

# Combining the data together for the Gotanda data
tpl_data_Go <- rbind(tpl_data_Go_females, tpl_data_Go_males)

# Subsetting down to information we need for comparison between
# methods
tpl_data_Go1 <- tpl_data_Go %>%
  dplyr::select(c("Site", "H", "diffvar", "Sex"))
tpl_data_Go1$Transportation <- "Individual Bags"
guppygyro1 <- FS_trin %>%
  dplyr::select(c("Site", "H", "diffvar", "sex"))
guppygyro1$Sex <- guppygyro1$sex
guppygyro1 <- guppygyro1 %>%
  dplyr::select(-c("sex"))
guppygyro1$Transportation <- "Bucket"
tpl_data_MJ <- tpl_data_MJ_males %>%
  dplyr::select(c("Site", "H", "diffvar", "Sex"))
tpl_data_MJ$Transportation <- "River Screen"

# Combining transportation data together for comparison
Transdata <- rbind(tpl_data_Go1, guppygyro1, tpl_data_MJ)

```

2 The feasible set accurately predicts the aggregation of neutralist barnacle on their limpet hosts

2.1 The difference in variance between the observed and feasible set of barnacles among limpets does not significantly differ from zero

2.1.1 One-Sample T-test for Limpet-barnacles

```
# conducting a one sample t-test to see if the difference in variance  
# between the observed distribution of barnacles on limpets and that  
# which is predicted by the feasible set are not different from zero  
ttestLimpetsDiffvar <- lmer(diffvar ~ 1 + (1 | Site), Limp)  
# Printing the results for the t-test  
summary(ttestLimpetsDiffvar)
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [  
## lmerModLmerTest]  
## Formula: diffvar ~ 1 + (1 | Site)  
## Data: Limp  
##  
## REML criterion at convergence: 19.6  
##  
## Scaled residuals:  
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max  
## -2.6749 -0.7255 -0.1109 0.6131 3.1805  
##  
## Random effects:  
## Groups Name Variance Std.Dev.  
## Site (Intercept) 0.006357 0.07973  
## Residual 0.058936 0.24277  
## Number of obs: 303, groups: Site, 9  
##  
## Fixed effects:  
## Estimate Std. Error df t value Pr(>|t|)  
## (Intercept) 0.01104 0.03036 7.83913 0.364 0.726
```

2.1.2 Visually inspecting this pattern

```
# Visual plot showing a boxplot and jittered points of the difference  
# in variance values for Limpets  
ggplot(Limp, aes(y = diffvar, x = L)) + geom_boxplot(aes(), fill = "light blue",  
width = 0.5) + theme_classic() + geom_hline(yintercept = 0) + xlab(" ") +  
ylab("Difference in variance (Obs.-Exp.)") + geom_jitter(color = "grey33")
```


2.2 Aggregation in the limpet-barnacle system decreases with mean length but increases with variance in length

2.2.1 Checking for collinearity and non-linear relationships

```
pairs(~diffvar + VarWRS + MeanWRS + MeanLRS + VarLRS, lower.panel = panel.smooth,  
      diag.panel = panel.hist, upper.panel = panel.cor, data = Limp)
```


2.2.2 Developing the limpet aggregation model

We will use a linear mixed model to analyze how aggregation differs between populations and what factors are important for it in the limpet barnacle system. Site is included as a random term to allow for non-independence of populations taken from the same site.

- Deterministic
- $DVL_{det} = a + b_1 \text{VarW} + b_2 \text{VarL} + b_3 \text{MeanL} + a_i$
- Stochastic
 - $DVL \sim N(DVL_{det}, \sigma^2)$
 - $a_i \sim N(0, \sigma_{Site}^2)$
- Fixed
 - VarWRS
 - VarLRS
 - MeanLRS
- Random
 - Site

2.2.3 Fitting the limpet aggregation model

```
Limpmo <- lmer(diffvar ~ VarWRS + VarLRS + MeanLRS + (1 | Site), Limp)
summary(Limpmo)
```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula: diffvar ~ VarWRS + VarLRS + MeanLRS + (1 | Site)
## Data: Limp
##
## REML criterion at convergence: -2
##
## Scaled residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -2.8029 -0.6494 -0.1110 0.6437 3.1848
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Variance Std.Dev.
## Site (Intercept) 0.004822 0.06944
## Residual 0.052194 0.22846
## Number of obs: 303, groups: Site, 9
##
## Fixed effects:
## Estimate Std. Error df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) 0.008063 0.027013 7.179720 0.299 0.7738
## VarWRS 0.003614 0.019296 295.046145 0.187 0.8516
## VarLRS 0.091709 0.019078 292.056845 4.807 2.45e-06 ***
## MeanLRS -0.046410 0.020942 152.509263 -2.216 0.0282 *
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
## (Intr) VarWRS VarLRS
## VarWRS 0.019
## VarLRS -0.020 -0.653
## MeanLRS 0.069 0.525 -0.533

```

2.2.4 Model validation for the limpet aggregation model

```

sim_residuals_DiffvarL <- simulateResiduals(Limpmod, 1000) #Quantile residuals
plot(sim_residuals_DiffvarL)

```

DHARMA residual


```
testDispersion(sim_residuals_DiffvarL)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p -value (two.sided) = 0.826

##

```
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 0.97884, p-value = 0.826
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
check_model(Limpmod, check = c("qq", "normality", "homogeneity"))
```

Homogeneity of Variance

Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Normality of Residuals

Dots should fall along the line

Normality of Residuals

Distribution should be close to the normal curve


```
# Residuals against the variables in the model. Excluded for space
# but they have been checked plotResiduals(sim_residuals_DiffvarL,
# FS_trin$sex) #Residual plot against sex
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_DiffvarL, FS_trin$Course)#Residual plot
# against Course plotResiduals(sim_residuals_DiffvarL,
# FS_trin$jonvarRS)#Residual plot against scaled jonvar
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_DiffvarL, FS_trin$jonresRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled jonres plotResiduals(sim_residuals_DiffvarL,
# FS_trin$meanLenRS)#Residual plot against scaled mean length
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_DiffvarL, FS_trin$logmeanRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled log mean parasites
```

2.2.5 ANOVA with Conditional F test with KR df for the limpet aggregation model

```
# Anova with a F test wiht KR correction for df
AnovaLimpmodel <- Anova(Limpmod, Type = 2, test.statistic = "F")
```

```
# Printing the results
AnovaLimpmodel
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
##
## Response: diffvar
##           F Df Df.res    Pr(>F)
## VarWRS    0.0343  1 295.15  0.85316
## VarLRS   22.5145  1 292.24 3.268e-06 ***
## MeanLRS   4.5443  1 154.58  0.03461 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

2.2.6 Important plots from the limpet aggregation model

3 The feasible set does not accurately predict the aggregation of *Gyrodactylus* spp. parasites among their guppy hosts

3.1 *Gyrodactylus* spp. are less aggregated on their guppy hosts than is to be expected given the feasible set.

3.1.1 One-Sample T-test for guppy-gyrodactylid overall

```
#conducting a one sample t-test to see if the difference in variance between the observed distribution and the expected distribution is significant
ttestGuppiesAll<-lmer(diffvar~1+(1|Site), FS_trin)
#Printing the results of the t-test
summary(ttestGuppiesAll)
```

3.1.2 Correlation test to elucidate whether diffvar from sexes at the same site is correlated

3.1.3 Test to see if transportation method impacts host-parasite distribution

```
# Building linear mixed model to compare transportation methods

lmtrans <- lmer(diffvar ~ H + Transportation + Sex + Transportation:H +
  (1 | Site), Transdata)
# Summary of transportation model
summary(lmtrans)
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula: diffvar ~ H + Transportation + Sex + Transportation:H + (1 |
## Site)
## Data: Transdata
##
## REML criterion at convergence: 96
##
## Scaled residuals:
```

```

##      Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
## -1.75546 -0.49652 -0.02122  0.41850  2.81801
##
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name            Variance Std.Dev.
## Site     (Intercept) 0.02867  0.1693
## Residual                0.06680  0.2585
## Number of obs: 132, groups: Site, 82
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error      df t value
## (Intercept)   -1.061e-01  7.922e-02  1.031e+02  -1.339
## H              -5.003e-04  2.468e-03  9.429e+01  -0.203
## TransportationIndividual Bags -1.359e-01  2.753e-01  8.078e+01  -0.494
## TransportationRiver Screen    5.533e-02  2.369e-01  1.199e+02   0.234
## SexM           -5.537e-02  4.890e-02  7.112e+01  -1.132
## H:TransportationIndividual Bags 3.614e-03  5.515e-03  8.327e+01   0.655
## H:TransportationRiver Screen  -2.742e-03  5.972e-03  1.154e+02  -0.459
##
##              Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)           0.184
## H                      0.840
## TransportationIndividual Bags 0.623
## TransportationRiver Screen  0.816
## SexM                   0.261
## H:TransportationIndividual Bags 0.514
## H:TransportationRiver Screen  0.647
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) H      TrnsIB TrnsRS SexM   H:TrIB
## H              -0.848
## TrnsprttnIB -0.263  0.238
## TrnsprttnRS -0.266  0.266  0.084
## SexM          -0.329  0.088  0.020 -0.097
## H:TrnsprtIB  0.385 -0.449 -0.945 -0.112 -0.055
## H:TrnsprtRS  0.350 -0.413 -0.098 -0.892 -0.036  0.183

```

```

# F test for significance
Anova(lmtrans, test.statistic = "F")

```

```

## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
##
## Response: diffvar
##
##              F Df Df.res Pr(>F)
## H              0.0172  1 91.202 0.8961
## Transportation  0.3733  2 94.610 0.6895
## Sex            1.2714  1 64.161 0.2637
## H:Transportation 0.3840  2 93.379 0.6822

```

```

# Testing the model to make sure it meets assumptions
# sim_residuals_Trans <-simulateResiduals(lmtrans, 1000) #Quantile
# residuals plot(sim_residuals_Trans)
# testDispersion(sim_residuals_Trans)

```

```

# graphing the transportation data
cbp1 <- c("#E69F00", "#56B4E9")

Transplot <- ggplot(Transdata, aes(Transportation, diffvar, Group = Sex,
  fill = Sex)) + geom_boxplot() + theme_classic() + ylab("Difference in Variance") +
  xlab("Transport Method") + geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed") +
  scale_fill_manual(values = cbp1) + theme(legend.position = "none") +
  geom_jitter()

print(Transplot)

```


Gyrodactylid parasites have similar distributions among their hosts, despite differences in survey methodology. To test how animal handling may affect our results, we used data from three studies of populations of guppies, *Poecilia reticulata*, infected with *Gyrodactylus* spp. Gotanda et al. (2012) separated guppy hosts into individual bags before transporting them to a field station and screening them for parasites (‘Bag transport’). Martin and Johnsen (2007) held guppies together in a bucket for ~30 minutes while screening them for parasites riverside (‘River Screen’). We transported guppies to the field station together in buckets before screening. Gyrodactylids showed similar distribution patterns across populations despite these differences (Transportation effect, $F=0.373$, $Df=94.61$, $P=0.690$), suggesting parasite transmission during and after capture may be minimal. Difference in variance (our aggregation metric) is the \log_{10} variance of the observed parasite distribution minus the \log_{10} variance of their feasible set median variance, so 0 (dashed line on the figure) represents that the feasible set accurately predicts parasite aggregation. The box and whiskers show the median value (bold horizontal line), the interquartile range (box), and the 95% range of the data (whiskers) for parasites on female (orange) and male (blue) guppies.

3.1.4 Taylor Power law comparison graph for the guppies

```
# Setting sex color screen
cbp1 <- c("#E69F00", "#56B4E9")
# geom_boxplot(data=Limp, aes(L,diffvar), fill='light blue',
# width=0.5)+geom_jitter(data=Limp, #aes(L,diffvar), width=0.4)
ggplot(FS_trin, aes(log10(MeanP), log10(VarP))) + geom_jitter() + theme_classic() +
  xlab("Mean Parasite Load") + ylab("Variance in Parasite Load") + geom_smooth(method = "lm") +
  scale_fill_manual(values = cbp1) + theme(legend.position = "none")
```



```
# Model for testing TPL
TPLlm <- lmer(log10(VarP) ~ log10(MeanP) + (1 | Site), FS_trin)
# Summary to examine TPL
summary(TPLlm)
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula: log10(VarP) ~ log10(MeanP) + (1 | Site)
## Data: FS_trin
##
## REML criterion at convergence: 58.8
##
## Scaled residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
```

```
## -2.50304 -0.53621 -0.03384  0.48634  2.72828
##
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name              Variance Std.Dev.
## Site     (Intercept) 0.02948  0.1717
## Residual                    0.08190  0.2862
## Number of obs: 86, groups: Site, 53
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error      df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  0.45400    0.04019  56.03575   11.30 4.54e-16 ***
## log10(MeanP) 1.61341    0.07888  65.17485   20.45 < 2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr)
## log10(MenP) -0.211
```

3.1.5 Visually inspecting this pattern

```
# Correlation test to test for the correlation in the aggregation of
# parasites among males and females from the same site
cor.test(FeasCorr$FemaleDiff, FeasCorr$MaleDiff)
```

```
##
## Pearson's product-moment correlation
##
## data: FeasCorr$FemaleDiff and FeasCorr$MaleDiff
## t = 1.644, df = 31, p-value = 0.1103
## alternative hypothesis: true correlation is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -0.06659884  0.57098297
## sample estimates:
##          cor
## 0.2831849
```

4 The average length and host sex are important drivers of aggregation in the guppy-*Gyrodactylus* spp. system

4.1 *Gyrodactylus* spp. aggregation decreases as mean length increases in guppy populations and is less aggregated among male than female guppies

4.1.1 Visually inspect our data for correlations or non-linear relationships

```
pairs(~diffvar + sex + Course + VarLenR + jonres + MeanLen + logMean, lower.panel = panel.smooth,
      diag.panel = panel.hist, upper.panel = panel.cor, data = FS_trin)
```


4.1.2 Developing the *Gyrodactylus* aggregation model

We used a linear mixed model to analyze how aggregation differs between populations and what factors are important for it. Site is included as a random term to allow for non-independence of female and male populations taken from the same site.

- Deterministic
- $DV_{det} = a + b_1 \text{Course} + b_2 \text{MeanLen} + b_3 \text{Sex} + b_4 \text{VarLenR} + b_5 \text{jonres} + b_6 \text{logMean} + a_i$
- Stochastic
 - $DV \sim N(DV_{det}, \sigma^2)$
 - $a_i \sim N(0, \sigma_{Site}^2)$
- Fixed
 - Course
 - MeanLen
 - Sex
 - VarLenR - residuals from a regression of variance in length and sex
 - Jonres
 - logMean
- Random
 - Site

4.1.3 Fitting the *Gyrodactylus* Aggregation model

```

# fitting a linear mixed model with all the covariates we think are
# important for this analysis.
Aggmodel <- lmer(diffvar ~ sex + Course + jonresRS + VarLenRS + MeanLenRS +
  logMeanRS + (1 | Site), data = FS_trin)

# Summary for the aggregation model
summary(Aggmodel)

## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula:
## diffvar ~ sex + Course + jonresRS + VarLenRS + MeanLenRS + logMeanRS +
## (1 | Site)
## Data: FS_trin
##
## REML criterion at convergence: 60.8
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.74056 -0.53691  0.08389  0.52270  2.44020
##
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name              Variance Std.Dev.
## Site     (Intercept)  0.02899  0.1703
## Residual                    0.06137  0.2477
## Number of obs: 86, groups: Site, 53
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error    df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.14805    0.03678 50.30198  -4.026 0.000191 ***
## sex1         0.08769    0.03369 62.88490   2.603 0.011508 *
## Course1     -0.03082    0.03673 56.04456  -0.839 0.405025
## jonresRS     0.02446    0.03904 78.26953   0.626 0.532868
## VarLenRS     0.04956    0.03928 72.32701   1.262 0.211061
## MeanLenRS   -0.11254    0.04152 76.14209  -2.710 0.008302 **
## logMeanRS    0.08710    0.03605 63.46901   2.416 0.018569 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##      (Intr) sex1  Cours1  jnrRS  VrLnRS  MnLnRS
## sex1      -0.154
## Course1   -0.139  0.012
## jonresRS  -0.026  0.101  0.052
## VarLenRS  0.018  0.105 -0.140 -0.480
## MeanLenRS 0.058 -0.547  0.126 -0.228 -0.204
## logMeanRS 0.059  0.050 -0.125 -0.054  0.215 -0.152

```

4.1.4 Model validation for the *Gyrodactylus* aggregation model

```

sim_residuals_Diffvar <- simulateResiduals(Aggmodel, 1000) #Quantile residuals
plot(sim_residuals_Diffvar)

```

DHARMA residual


```
testDispersion(sim_residuals_Diffvar)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

##

```
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 0.94212, p-value = 0.738
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
check_model(Aggmodel, check = c("qq", "normality", "homogeneity"))
```

Homogeneity of Variance

Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Normality of Residuals

Dots should fall along the line

Normality of Residuals

Distribution should be close to the normal curve


```
# Residuals against the variables in the model. Excluded for space
# but they have been checked plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffvar,
# FS_trin$sex) #Residual plot against sex
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffvar, FS_trin$Course)#Residual plot
# against Course plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffvar,
# FS_trin$jonvarRS)#Residual plot against scaled jonvar
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffvar, FS_trin$jonresRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled jonres plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffvar,
# FS_trin$meanLenRS)#Residual plot against scaled mean length
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffvar, FS_trin$logmeanRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled log mean parasites
```

4.1.5 ANOVA with Conditional F test with KR df for *Gyrodactylus* aggregation model

```
# Anova with a F test wiht KR correction for df
AnovaAggmodel <- Anova(Aggmodel, Type = 2, test.statistic = "F")
```

```
# Printing the results
AnovaAggmodel
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
##
## Response: diffvar
##           F Df Df.res  Pr(>F)
## sex       6.6492  1 59.519 0.012412 *
## Course    0.6937  1 51.866 0.408715
## jonresRS  0.3776  1 78.069 0.540670
## VarLenRS  1.5197  1 70.672 0.221753
## MeanLenRS 7.0974  1 75.386 0.009436 **
## logMeanRS 5.7439  1 60.189 0.019669 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

4.1.6 Important plots from the *Gyrodactylus* aggregation model

```
VSLM <- visreg(Aggmodel, "logMeanRS", scale = "response", partial = TRUE,
  plot = F)

VSLMf <- VSLM$fit
VSLMr <- VSLM$res

ggplot(data = VSLMr, aes(logMeanRS, visregRes)) + geom_smooth(data = VSLMr,
  aes(logMeanRS, visregRes), method = "lm") + geom_hline(yintercept = 0,
  linetype = "dashed") + geom_jitter(data = VSLMr, aes(logMeanRS, visregRes)) +
  xlab("logMeanRS") + ylab("Difference in Variance (Obs. - Exp.)") +
  theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14))
```


4.2 Guppy populations have higher prevalences than the feasible set in populations with higher mean length

4.2.1 Checking for collinearity and non-linear relationships

```
# Visual plot to examine collinearity and non-linear relationships
# for prevalence data
pairs(~DiffPrev + sex + Course + ResBC + VarLenR + jonres + MeanLen + logMean,
      lower.panel = panel.smooth, diag.panel = panel.hist, upper.panel = panel.cor,
      data = FS_trin)
```


4.2.2 One-Sample T-test for guppy-gyrodactylid Prevalence overall

```
# conducting a one sample t-test to see if the difference in variance
# between the observed distribution of Gyrodactylids on guppies and
# that which is predicted by the feasible set are not different from
# zero
ttestGuppiesAll <- lmer(DiffPrev ~ 1 + (1 | Site), FS_trin)
# Printing the results of the t-test
summary(ttestGuppiesAll)
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula: DiffPrev ~ 1 + (1 | Site)
## Data: FS_trin
##
## REML criterion at convergence: -130.3
##
## Scaled residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -2.46282 -0.67897 -0.03292 0.55534 2.50898
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Variance Std.Dev.
## Site (Intercept) 0.001237 0.03517
## Residual 0.010823 0.10403
## Number of obs: 86, groups: Site, 53
##
## Fixed effects:
```

```
##           Estimate Std. Error      df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) 0.08678    0.01229 51.24725   7.062 4.24e-09 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

4.2.3 Developing the Prevalence model

We used a linear mixed model with a site random effect to account for non-independence between males and females at the same site:

- Deterministic
- $DP_{det} = a + b_1\text{Course} + b_2\text{MeanLen} + b_3\text{Sex} + b_4\text{jonvar} + b_5\text{jonres} + b_6\text{logMean} + a_i$
- Stochastic
 - $DP \sim N(DP_{det}, \sigma^2)$
 - $a_i \sim N(0, \sigma_{Site}^2)$
- Fixed
 - Course
 - MeanLen
 - Sex
 - VarLenR
 - Jonres
 - logMean
- Random
 - Site

4.2.4 Fitting the Prevalence model

```
# linear mixed model with all predictors
modelPrev <- lmer(DiffPrev ~ sex + Course + jonresRS + VarLenRS + MeanLenRS +
  logMeanRS + (1 | Site), data = FS_trin)

# Summary for prevalence model output
summary(modelPrev)
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula:
## DiffPrev ~ sex + Course + jonresRS + VarLenRS + MeanLenRS + logMeanRS +
## (1 | Site)
## Data: FS_trin
##
## REML criterion at convergence: -97.9
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.64325 -0.57817 -0.02042  0.54246  2.35831
```

```

##
## Random effects:
##   Groups   Name      Variance Std.Dev.
##   Site     (Intercept) 0.001455 0.03815
##   Residual                0.010202 0.10101
## Number of obs: 86, groups: Site, 53
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error      df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  0.086277   0.012453  47.299655   6.928 1.02e-08 ***
## sex1         -0.017484   0.012989  61.434273  -1.346  0.18321
## Course1      0.019374   0.012574  52.278848   1.541  0.12940
## jonresRS     -0.017008   0.014378  78.969456  -1.183  0.24039
## VarLenRS     -0.004984   0.014721  76.938373  -0.339  0.73585
## MeanLenRS    0.039880   0.014854  73.465492   2.685  0.00896 **
## logMeanRS   -0.010126   0.012543  61.577256  -0.807  0.42261
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) sex1   Cours1 jnrsRS VrLnRS MnLnRS
## sex1          -0.156
## Course1       -0.140 -0.001
## jonresRS      -0.023  0.099  0.044
## VarLenRS      0.009  0.109 -0.139 -0.486
## MeanLenRS     0.054 -0.505  0.157 -0.208 -0.223
## logMeanRS     0.025  0.083 -0.125 -0.045  0.229 -0.161

```

4.2.5 Model validation for the Prevalence model

```

# Quantile residuals
sim_residuals_Diffprev <- simulateResiduals(modelPrev, 1000)
plot(sim_residuals_Diffprev)

```

DHARMA residual


```
testDispersion(sim_residuals_Diffprev)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p -value (two.sided) = 0.668

##

```
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 0.93007, p-value = 0.668
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
check_model(modelPrev, check = c("qq", "normality", "homogeneity"))
```

Homogeneity of Variance

Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Normality of Residuals

Dots should fall along the line

Normality of Residuals

Distribution should be close to the normal curve


```
# Residuals against the variables in the model. Excluded for space
# but they have been checked and code is included to facilitate
# exploring them plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffprev, FS_trin$sex)
# #Residual plot against sex plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffprev,
# FS_trin$Course)#Residual plot against Course
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffprev, FS_trin$jonvarRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled jonvar plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffprev,
# FS_trin$jonresRS)#Residual plot against scaled jonres
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffprev, FS_trin$meanLenRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled mean length
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_Diffprev, FS_trin$logmeanRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled log mean parasites
```

4.2.6 ANOVA with Conditional F test with Kenward-Roger df for significance in Prevalence model

```

# Anova to run F test with KR correciton for df
AnovamodelPrev <- Anova(modelPrev, type = 2, test.statistic = "F")
# Printing the results
AnovamodelPrev

## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
##
## Response: DiffPrev
##           F Df Df.res Pr(>F)
## sex       1.7811  1 59.221 0.18712
## Course    2.3361  1 49.466 0.13278
## jonresRS  1.3497  1 78.964 0.24883
## VarLenRS  0.1094  1 76.602 0.74175
## MeanLenRS 6.9803  1 72.610 0.01009 *
## logMeanRS 0.6398  1 59.376 0.42697
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

4.2.7 Both males and females have higher prevalences than the feasible set

4.2.8 One-sample t-test for both sexes

```

# One way t-test to test whether the number of infected individuals
# is significantly different than zero
ttestprevf <- t.test(FS_trin$DiffPrev[FS_trin$sex == "F"])
# Printing the results
ttestprevf

```

```

##
## One Sample t-test
##
## data:  FS_trin$DiffPrev[FS_trin$sex == "F"]
## t = 5.6233, df = 48, p-value = 9.381e-07
## alternative hypothesis: true mean is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
##  0.05548548 0.11724584
## sample estimates:
## mean of x
## 0.08636566

```

```

# One way t-test to test whether the number of infected individuals
# is significantly different than zero
ttestprevm <- t.test(FS_trin$DiffPrev[FS_trin$sex == "M"])
# Printing teh results
ttestprevm

```

```

##
## One Sample t-test
##
## data:  FS_trin$DiffPrev[FS_trin$sex == "M"]

```

```
## t = 4.8202, df = 36, p-value = 2.599e-05
## alternative hypothesis: true mean is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 0.05242467 0.12858245
## sample estimates:
## mean of x
## 0.09050356
```

4.2.9 Important plots from the prevalence model

4.3 Populations with larger guppy individuals have less parasites on the heaviest infected individual and male guppies have less parasites on their heaviest infected host than the feasible set

4.3.1 Checking for collinearity and non-linear relationships

```
# Looking at collinearity and non-linear relationships for Parasite
# ratio
pairs(~log10(DiffPRatio) + sex + Course + VarLenR + jonres + MeanLen +
      logMean, lower.panel = panel.smooth, diag.panel = panel.hist, upper.panel = panel.cor,
      data = FS_trin)
```


4.3.2 One-Sample T-test for guppy-gyrodactylid Prevalence overall

```
# conducting a one sample t-test to see if the difference in variance
# between the observed distribution of Gyrodactylids on guppies and
# that which is predicted by the feasible set are not different from
```

```

# zero
ttestGuppiesAllMaxP <- lmer(log10(DiffPRatio) ~ 1 + (1 | Site), FS_trin)
# Printing the results of the t-test
summary(ttestGuppiesAllMaxP)

```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula: log10(DiffPRatio) ~ 1 + (1 | Site)
## Data: FS_trin
##
## REML criterion at convergence: -16.4
##
## Scaled residuals:
## Min 1Q Median 3Q Max
## -1.99330 -0.54756 -0.07879 0.56777 2.30620
##
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Variance Std.Dev.
## Site (Intercept) 0.01591 0.1261
## Residual 0.03215 0.1793
## Number of obs: 86, groups: Site, 53
##
## Fixed effects:
## Estimate Std. Error df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.07913 0.02628 53.28196 -3.011 0.00397 **
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

4.3.3 Developing the log ratio of max intensity model

We used a linear mixed model with a site random effect to account for non-independence between males and females at the same site:

- Deterministic
- $\text{Log}_{10}(DP_{det}) = a + b_1\text{Course} + b_2\text{MeanLen} + b_3\text{Sex} + b_4\text{VarLenR} + b_5\text{jonres} + b_6\text{logMean} + a_i$
- Stochastic
 - $\text{Log}_{10}(\text{DP}) \sim N(\text{Log}_{10}(DP_{det}), \sigma^2)$
 - $a_i \sim N(0, \sigma_{\text{Site}}^2)$
- Fixed
 - Course
 - MeanLen
 - Sex
 - VarLenR - residual from a linear regression of variance in length and sex
 - Jonres - residual from a linear regression of body condition and mean length
 - logMean - log mean parasites
- Random
 - Site

4.3.4 Fitting the ratio of log max intensity model

```
# Linear mixed model to examine which variables are important for
# parasite ratio
LMaxInt <- lmer(log10(DiffPRatio) ~ sex + Course + VarLenRS + jonresRS +
  logMeanRS + MeanLenRS + (1 | Site), data = FS_trin)

# Printing the summary results
summary(LMaxInt)

## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula: log10(DiffPRatio) ~ sex + Course + VarLenRS + jonresRS + logMeanRS +
## MeanLenRS + (1 | Site)
## Data: FS_trin
##
## REML criterion at convergence: -0.1
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -1.55514 -0.46534  0.03869  0.49463  2.27887
##
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name                Variance Std.Dev.
## Site     (Intercept)  0.01634  0.1278
## Residual                    0.02629  0.1621
## Number of obs: 86, groups: Site, 53
##
## Fixed effects:
##              Estimate Std. Error    df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.08196    0.02568 49.88012  -3.192  0.00245 **
## sex1         0.06229    0.02250 62.42823   2.768  0.00741 **
## Course1     -0.02069    0.02554 56.06131  -0.810  0.42131
## VarLenRS     0.03176    0.02640 69.80054   1.203  0.23311
## jonresRS     0.02086    0.02645 77.68766   0.789  0.43258
## logMeanRS    0.07947    0.02495 63.15868   3.186  0.00224 **
## MeanLenRS   -0.07507    0.02842 76.78355  -2.641  0.01000 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) sex1  Cours1 VrLnRS jnrsRS lgMnRS
## sex1         -0.153
## Course1     -0.138  0.017
## VarLenRS     0.021  0.103 -0.140
## jonresRS    -0.027  0.101  0.057 -0.477
## logMeanRS   0.069  0.037 -0.125  0.210 -0.059
## MeanLenRS   0.060 -0.562  0.114 -0.198 -0.234 -0.149
```

4.3.5 Model validation for the log ratio of max intensity model

```
sim_residuals_LMaxInt <- simulateResiduals(LMaxInt, 1000) #Quantile residuals
plot(sim_residuals_LMaxInt)
```

DHARMA residual


```
testDispersion(sim_residuals_LMaxInt)
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p-value (two.sided) = 0.774

```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 0.94438, p-value = 0.774  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
check_model(LMaxInt, check = c("qq", "normality", "homogeneity"))
```

Homogeneity of Variance

Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Normality of Residuals

Dots should fall along the line

Normality of Residuals

Distribution should be close to the normal curve


```
# Residuals against the variables in the model. Excluded for space
# but they have been checked and code is included to facilitate
# exploring them plotResiduals(sim_residuals_LMaxInt, FS_trin$sex)
# #Residual plot against sex plotResiduals(sim_residuals_LMaxInt,
# FS_trin$Course)#Residual plot against Course
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_LMaxInt, FS_trin$jonvarRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled jonvar plotResiduals(sim_residuals_LMaxInt,
# FS_trin$jonresRS)#Residual plot against scaled jonres
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_LMaxInt, FS_trin$meanLenRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled mean length
# plotResiduals(sim_residuals_LMaxInt, FS_trin$logmeanRS)#Residual
# plot against scaled log mean parasites
```

4.3.6 ANOVA with Conditional F test with Kenward-Roger df for significance in log ratio of max intensity model

```
# Anova with Conditional F test with KR correction for df
Anova(LMaxInt, type = 2, test.statistic = "F")
```

```
## Analysis of Deviance Table (Type II Wald F tests with Kenward-Roger df)
##
## Response: log10(DiffPRatio)
##           F Df Df.res  Pr(>F)
## sex       7.5138  1 59.645 0.008068 **
## Course    0.6469  1 52.661 0.424853
## VarLenRS  1.3813  1 68.038 0.243976
```

```
## jonresRS 0.5983 1 77.402 0.441588
## logMeanRS 9.9864 1 60.462 0.002464 **
## MeanLenRS 6.7325 1 76.307 0.011347 *
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

4.3.7 Important plots from the log ratio of max intensity model

4.3.8 The log ratio of parasite burden on the heaviest infected host is significantly different from zero for male guppies but not female guppies

4.3.9 One-sample t-test for both males and females log ratio of max parasite burden

```
# t-test to test whether the log max parasite ratio in females is
# significantly different than zero
t.test(log10(FS_trin$DiffPRatio[FS_trin$sex == "F"]))
```

```
##
## One Sample t-test
##
## data: log10(FS_trin$DiffPRatio[FS_trin$sex == "F"])
## t = -1.8702, df = 48, p-value = 0.06756
## alternative hypothesis: true mean is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -0.117104743 0.004236819
## sample estimates:
## mean of x
## -0.05643396
```

```
# t-test to test whether the log max parasite ratio in males is
# significantly different than zero
t.test(log10(FS_trin$DiffPRatio[FS_trin$sex == "M"]))
```

```
##
## One Sample t-test
##
## data: log10(FS_trin$DiffPRatio[FS_trin$sex == "M"])
## t = -3.0896, df = 36, p-value = 0.003851
## alternative hypothesis: true mean is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## -0.19266996 -0.03996471
## sample estimates:
## mean of x
## -0.1163173
```